

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR
OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES
SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Peer Review Information Service for Monographs (PRISM)

DELIVERABLE 5.4

Laura J. Wilkinson / Ronald Snijder
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Abstract

This document provides a complete description of the work carried out regarding the Peer Review Information Service for Monographs (PRISM) through the OPERAS-PLUS project T5.4, including background and future plans.

This version has not yet been approved by the European project officer for OPERAS-PLUS.

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Executive summary

PRISM (Peer Review Information Service for Monographs) is a service provided by DOAB as part of the OPERAS service catalogue. PRISM is a structured way for academic publishers to display information about their peer review processes within a controlled vocabulary across their entire catalogue.

PRISM has been in the works for several years, with the first preparations starting in 2016 through European Funded HIRMEOS and OPERAS-P projects and now OPERAS-PLUS. PRISM originally began as “a certification service” for peer review procedures and open licences, at the level of publishers, books, and book chapters that was being developed within the HIRMEOS project with the pilot implementation for HIRMEOS platforms put in place by May 2018. Between May 2018 and September 2019, a beta version was built in the ‘old’ DOAB environment, by SemperTool.

The objective for PRISM within OPERAS-PLUS was to support the move to launching a production service (including onboarding of new participating publishers), which was achieved in November 2022. As part of launch preparations, it was decided to rename the service from “OPERAS Certification Service” to “PRISM” (Peer Review Information Service for Monographs) to better reflect the function of PRISM as making available metadata about a publisher’s peer review procedure(s), and does not certify the procedures as such. We moved away from talking about a “certification service” because there is no validation phase in the process (and has never been); it’s purely a mechanism for publishers to expose metadata about their peer review practices.

Due to the complexity of the peer review landscape, in which many different practices exist, it is neither feasible nor desirable to certify or value some methods of academic quality control at the expense of others. We aim to support a diverse range of practices across different subject areas, countries, and cultural and linguistic domains. Therefore, we established a broadly applicable set of peer review characteristics, from which publishers select options to describe their practices, and which readers and other stakeholders can use to understand how a work has been checked for academic quality. For these reasons, OAPEN staff (and as a Foundation) does not give any opinion or guidance on which peer review practice(s) to follow. This is a decision and a discussion for academic communities, not infrastructure providers.

Thanks to OPERAS-PLUS, the PRISM service is now in production, steadily increasing the number of publishers and peer review information records.

1. Introduction

PRISM aims to provide information from open access (OA) book publishers, based on their publishing practices, in particular their peer review procedure. The service is intended to enable publishers to provide information at both publisher level and individual publication level. The goal of the service is to support trust in OA book publishing, by improving transparency around quality assurance of OA book publishers and their publications.

Due to the complexity of the peer review landscape, in which many different practices exist, it is neither feasible nor desirable to certify or value some methods of academic quality control at the expense of others. We aim to support a diverse range of practices across different subject areas, countries, and cultural and linguistic domains. Therefore, we established a broadly applicable set of peer review characteristics, from which publishers select options to describe their practices, and which readers and other stakeholders can use to understand how a work has been checked for academic quality.

For these reasons, OAPEN staff (and as a Foundation) does not give any opinion or guidance on which peer review practice(s) to follow. This is a decision and a discussion for academic communities, not infrastructure providers.

The overall structure of the document follows the standardised template that OPERAS uses as part of its Service Portfolio Management (SPM) process, which was originally based on the FitSM standard template called “Service Design and Transition Package”¹. Each of the individual OPERAS services will follow a similar structure, which will enable all content generated to be directly used within the OPERAS service management system (SMS).

Therefore, this document is structured as follows:

- Section 1: introduces the document and its structure.
- Section 2: describes the background of the service, previous funding and relevant development activities as an orientation to the service status at the start of OPERAS-PLUS and thus objectives within it..
- Section 3: outlines the value proposition including customer and user profiles.
- Section 4: presents the business case including demand assessment, assumptions, costs and risks, among others.
- Section 5: moves into the service design including service requirements, high

¹ <https://www.fitsm.eu/downloads/#toggle-id-5>

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- level technical architecture, order workflows, acceptance criteria, among others.
- Section 6: starts the transition phase to shift the service into a live environment and the related activities and timing required.
 - Section 7: provides the current status of the service along with visualisations.
 - Section 8: concludes the overall document.

2. Background

PRISM has been in the works for several years, with the first preparations starting in 2016. It has been made possible thanks to European Funding through the HIRMEOS and OPERAS-P projects and now OPERAS-PLUS.

PRISM originally began as “a certification service” for peer review procedures and open licences, at the level of publishers, books, and book chapters that was being developed within the HIRMEOS project with the pilot implementation for HIRMEOS platforms put in place by May 2018. Between May 2018 and September 2019, a beta version was built in the ‘old’ DOAB environment, by SemperTool.

The OPERAS-P project phase (2019-2021) allowed for some re-conceptualization and development with the following objectives:

- Secure DOAB as central service of OPERAS on an open source platform
- Integrate DOAB and the OAPEN Library into one technical solution, based on DSpace
- Rebuild the “certification service” in the new environment

Therefore, the objective for PRISM within OPERAS-PLUS was to support the move to launching a production service (including onboarding of new participating publishers), which was achieved in November 2022. As part of launch preparations, it was decided to rename the service from “OPERAS Certification Service” to “PRISM” (Peer Review Information Service for Monographs) to better reflect the function of PRISM as making available metadata about a publisher’s peer review procedure(s), and does not certify the procedures as such. We moved away from talking about a “certification service” because there is no validation phase in the process (and has never been); it’s purely a mechanism for publishers to expose metadata about their peer review practices.

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3. Value Proposition

User Profile	Description
(Potential) Customer of the service	<p>Publishers seeking to publicise the quality assurance processes of their (open access) book publications.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publishers are able to provide information about their quality assurance (peer-review) process in a structured way within a controlled vocabulary • Builds trust in Open Access book publishing and is a first step towards more clarity and transparency in OA books peer-review practices • PRISM collects practices from hundreds of monograph publishing houses, categorises them, and publishes them all through a single access point
(Potential) User of the service	<p>Publishers add the content: they create PRISM records (one for each peer review process they use), and link their works in DOAB to the corresponding PRISM record.</p> <p>End-users: Librarians and readers can see PRISM information and use it to make decisions about the authority of a work.</p>
User profile (pains/gains)	<p>At the publisher level, all their peer review processes are visible (as they may have more than one process in use across all their series and titles).</p> <p>At the level of an individual publication, the peer review process applied to that work is displayed.</p> <p>Pain points for users:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Without a transparent description of the quality process of the publication, it becomes harder to dispel the myth of open access books being of inferior quality. <p>Benefits to each user group:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publishers: PRISM helps them to display the peer review process that has been applied to books in their collection. This helps them showcase how they apply best practices in peer review. • Librarians: PRISM allows them to see the quality control process that applies to a given book. This will give them

User Profile	Description
	<p>confidence in recommending the book as a reliable source to their researchers and students.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funders: PRISM gives them more detailed information about the quality assurance process of the research outputs they've funded. • Researchers, students, or general readers: PRISM allows you to see the quality control process that applies to a given book. This gives you more information about the publisher.
Service Description	<p>PRISM gives publishers the opportunity to display information about their peer review procedures in a structured way within a controlled vocabulary (for details, please see Section 7.2 Current documentation for PRISM), enables inclusion of information as part of the book's metadata and builds trust in OA book publishing by improving transparency around the quality assurance process. PRISM collects the variety of peer reviewing practices from hundreds of monograph publishing houses, categorises them, and provides a single access point to the list of certified peer reviewed monographs available in Open Access in the world.</p>
Service Area	Quality Assurance
Service tags	Peer review, Transparency, Processes
Value Proposition (pain relievers / gain creators)	<p>PRISM is a structured way for academic publishers to display information about their peer review processes within a controlled vocabulary across their entire catalogue. PRISM's goal is to provide transparency about the peer review process(es) that apply to their works. This helps build trust in open access academic book publishing.</p>
Tagline	<p>Increasing trust in Open Access book publishing by improving transparency around the quality assurance process (peer review procedure).</p>
Service Criticality	PRISM is considered a value-added service for DOAB

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User Profile	Description
EOSC Marketplace	https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/operas-certification-d-oab

Table 1: Value Proposition Design

4. Business Case Design

	Best Case	Average Case	Worst Case
Demand assessment	<p>Hundreds of publishers will want to expose their peer review information</p> <p>Librarians and other stakeholders demand this service from publishers.</p>	<p>Tens of publishers will want to expose their peer review information</p> <p>Librarians and other stakeholders expect this service from publishers.</p>	<p><10 publishers will want to expose their peer review information</p> <p>Librarians and other stakeholders appreciate but don't expect this service from publishers.</p>
Assumptions (about uptake)	Hundreds of publishers take up the service	Tens of publishers take up the service	<10 publishers take up the service
Expected organisational impact	OAPEN staff can absorb the extra workload; receive additional funding	OAPEN staff can absorb the extra workload; some other projects might be delayed; current resources are sufficient to operate the services	Lack of OAPEN staffing / capacity to continue offering service or costs become too high versus cost recovery
Expected Cost	No extra staff or technical infrastructure cost; financial resources	No extra staff or technical infrastructure costs	Need to recruit extra staff to help cover the workload

	Best Case	Average Case	Worst Case
	provide means for upgrades	needed to provide minimum impact	
Expected Revenue / Cost Recovery	Additional funding generated through national and/or EU projects/grants	Fixed budget line item of the DOAB budget	Cost losses are absorbed as part of other DOAB services
Risks	Successful uptake	Minimal uptake; technical functionality limited	No demand or too much demand related to resources available
Supplier Evaluation	Specialist technical support for DSpace		
Constraints / limiting factors	Funding, human effort, technical competence		
Competitors and/or similar services	None known		
Pricing and/or Access Policy	No charge for publishers to participate in PRISM, but they do have to join DOAB and there are some conditions for this. Access to PRISM information is free and without restrictions (no licence/restrictions apply)		

Table 2: Business Case Design

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5. Service Design

5.1. Service Requirements

Functional and technical	PRISM is an additional element of publisher metadata in DOAB. Both front-end and back-end managed via DSpace 6. AAI: log-in function and user management via EGI Check-in.
Availability, continuity and performance-related	The PRISM element of DSpace had to be in place; DOAB registration form, EGI Check-in authentication, supporting documentation in DOAB Publishers' Guide and on DOAB website. The PRISM should be available 24/7 with the availability target of 95-98% availability.
Security and data protection-related	No specific sensitive data is and will be managed in the PRISM and no personal data is collected either. Data and security policies all DOAB policies are applied to PRISM.
Usability-related	PRISM is a user facing service, therefore the UI must be easy to use for data entry.
Organisational	Internal workflow for dealing with PRISM submissions; workflow for new publishers joining DOAB.
Data sources	Manually provided by each publisher.

Table 3: Service Requirements

5.2. Service Architecture

High-level service architecture	Type	Service Components	Description	Suppliers	TRL
	Enabling	DSpace	Open source software needed to run DOAB	Atmire	9
	Enabling	Check-in	Authentication and authorization	EGI Foundation	9

Table 4: Service Architecture

5.3. Service Order Workflow

Step	Role	Description
1	Customer (publisher)	Publisher logs in to DOAB, completes one or more PRISM submissions

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Step	Role	Description
2	Service Provider	Checks each PRISM submission (to ensure all fields completed and anything in the free-text field looks sensible) and confirms it as a PRISM record
3	Customer (publisher)	Receives email notification that PRISM record has been confirmed
4	Customer (publisher)	Publisher links their work(s) to the relevant PRISM record
5	Customer (end user)	Librarians, readers, researchers, and other stakeholders can see PRISM information on the DOAB site and access it via the API

Table 5: Service Order Workflow

5.4. Service Acceptance Criteria

Category	Acceptance Criteria	Critical	Achieved
Functional and technical acceptance	PRISM module functional within DOAB infrastructure	Yes	Yes
Service Level and Reporting	Terms and conditions linked to DOAB	No	Yes
Customer and supplier related	Beta-testing for customer acceptance and usability feedback	Yes	Yes
	Atmire contract in place for DSpace	Yes	Yes
Capacity, availability, and performance-related	Assessment by Atmire to ensure related requirements	Yes	Yes
Security and data protection-related	Capabilities of the DSpace environment confirmed by Atmire	Yes	Yes
	Data policies linked to DOAB	Yes	Yes

Category	Acceptance Criteria	Critical	Achieved
Support related	Iterative development of documentation and training for OAPEN staff on how to support PRISM users	Yes	Yes
	Documentation for publishers about the aims of PRISM, the PRISM workflow, how to create a PRISM submission, and how to link PRISM records to works. OAPEN staff do not provide any guidance on peer review practices themselves.	Yes	Yes
Configuration, change and release related	Bulk update functionality (ability for publishers to link PRISM records with multiple works at once)	No	No
	Intermediaries functionality (ability for third parties to create PRISM submissions and link PRISM records to works on behalf of another publisher)	No	No
Usability related	Beta-testing for customer acceptance and usability feedback	Yes	Yes
Organisational	Ongoing monitoring of staff capacity	Yes	Yes
Other	N/A	–	–

Table 6: Service Acceptance Criteria

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5.5. Service Options

#	Name	Description
1	PRISM	The only option for a publisher is to use or not use the PRISM functionality; there is no customisation beyond the option of providing details of peer review when completing a PRISM submission, and then linking a PRISM record to a work

Table 7: Service Options

5.6. Service Requests

#	Name	Description
1	Help and support for using DOAB and/or PRISM	Email, attend one of our webinars, watch our webinar recording , read our documentation
2	Lost password	Reset password for DOAB

Table 8: Service Requests

5.7. Financial Structure

5.7.1. Costs

Item	Cost (PM or €)
Support	0.25 PM
Technical maintenance	0.1 PM + approx €5,000/yr

Table 9: Service Costs

5.7.2. Pricing Scheme

Item	Price
N/A	No pricing scheme is foreseen as PRISM is intended to be a free-at-point-of-delivery service.

Table 10: Pricing Scheme

5.7.3. Revenue Streams and/or Cost Recovery Measures

Revenue Source	Expected revenue (if applicable) Amount or a % of costs	Additional Info
DOAB	PRISM is supported by the overall DOAB budget.	–

Table 11: Revenue Streams and/or Cost Recovery Measures

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6. Service Transition Plan

6.1. Transition Plan

	Activities and timing	Responsibilities (RACI)	Progress report
Specification, negotiation and agreement	Completed in the course of OPERAS-P and continued in OPERAS-PLUS	T5.4/WP5	DONE
Development and procurement	Ensure Atmire contract covers PRISM	OAPEN staff	DONE
	Ensure agreement with EGI for Check-in	OAPEN staff	DONE
Initial Testing	Beta-testing for customer acceptance and usability feedback	OAPEN staff	DONE
Operation with early life support	Time resource/capacity analysis to ensure availability of potential increased demand	OAPEN staff	DONE
Regular operation	Reserving OAPEN staff capacity for providing PRISM support and set up generic mailbox and associated workflow	Fixed budget line item of the DOAB budget	DONE
Communication	Communication plan	OAPEN staff	DONE
	Blog post	OAPEN staff	DONE
	Webinars	OAPEN staff	DONE
	Community newsletter	OAPEN staff	DONE

Table 12: Transition Plan

6.2. Supporting Projects

Project name	Related task(s)	Activity Description	Period of activity	Effort (PMs)	Status
OPERAS-PLUS	T5.4	Implement the 2nd stage of development of the PRISM display function and improvement proposals publisher testing. Enable the service to be in production (TRL9)	Sep 2022 - Aug 2023	6	COMPLETE

Table 13: Supporting Projects

6.3. Final Service Phase Check-list

Service phase	Responsible	Description	Condition met	Notes / Evidence	Verification
Production Min. maturity = TRL8	OAPEN staff	Ensure all items of the transition plan are complete	Yes	OAPEN internal PRISM rollout planning meeting notes	OAPEN staff

Table 14: Supporting Projects

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7. Current Service Overview

The following information is available on the PRISM section of the DOAB website².

7.1. Overview

PRISM – Peer Review Information Service for Monographs is a service provided by DOAB as part of the OPERAS service catalogue³. DOAB (including PRISM) is overseen by a Scientific Committee⁴ which validates and reviews requirements, and acts as a Board of Appeal for complaints from publishers.

7.1.1. What are the benefits of PRISM?

PRISM is a standardised way for academic publishers to display information about their peer review processes across their entire catalogue. At the publisher level, all their peer review processes are visible (as they may have more than one process in use across all their series and titles). At the level of an individual publication, the peer review process applied to that work is displayed.

PRISM's goal is to provide transparency about the peer review process(es) that apply to their works. This helps build trust in open access academic book publishing.

7.1.2. How can PRISM help me?

If you're a publisher, PRISM helps you display the peer review process that has been applied to works in your collection. This helps you showcase how you apply best practices in peer review.

If you're a librarian, PRISM allows you to see the quality control process that applies to a given work. This will give you confidence in recommending the work as a reliable source to your researchers and students.

If you're a funder, PRISM gives you more detailed information about the quality assurance process of the research outputs you've funded.

If you're a researcher, student, or a general reader, PRISM allows you to see the quality control process that applies to a given work. This will give you more information about the publisher.

7.1.3. How can I see PRISM in action?

There are four ways to see PRISM at work:

² <https://doabooks.org/en/publishers/prism>

³ <https://operas-eu.org/services/prism/>

⁴ <https://www.doabooks.org/en/doab/purpose-of-doab>

1. On the DOAB site, you will see a PRISM logo next to a publisher. Click on the PRISM logo to see the details of the publisher's peer review process(es). You may see more than one process displayed, as some publishers apply different processes to different series or works.

Browsing by Publisher:

0-9 A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z

Now showing items 1-20 of 64

Publisher

Ubiquity Press [69]

2. On the DOAB site, you will see a PRISM logo next to a work. Click on the PRISM logo to see the detail of the peer review process that has been applied to the work.

[Show Advanced Filters](#)

Now showing items 1-10 of 294

 Export

3. See all the works in DOAB that have PRISM information using this query⁵.

Search

[Show Advanced Filters](#)

Now showing items 1-10 of 225

 Export

⁵ https://directory.doabooks.org/discover?query=peerreview.id%3A*

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4. PRISM peer review metadata is also available through the DOAB API⁶, which is freely distributed and incorporated into library search tools worldwide.

7.1.4. What are the PRISM terms?

Publishers can request to be included in PRISM if they agree to the terms and conditions of the service.

Publishers must provide correct information and may be suspended from using PRISM if there is evidence that the information they provided is incorrect. Such cases may be referred to the Scientific Committee, which acts as a Board of Appeal. Suspended publishers may be required to reapply for the service and their inclusion may be revoked. DOAB reserves the right to announce such measures through its media channels.

7.1.5. I'm a publisher - what do I need to do to participate in PRISM?

1. Prepare: you will need to provide DOAB with details of your peer review process(es), so it's important to spend time with colleagues (especially those on editorial boards) to collect this information and ensure it reflects the range of practices across your publications before moving on to the next steps. Learn more about how to prepare for PRISM in the DOAB publishers' guide⁷.
2. You need to be a member of DOAB. Joining DOAB⁸ is open to all academic publishers who meet our requirements of applying a peer review process to their academic books, and making their books available under an open access licence.
3. You log in to DOAB and create a PRISM peer review submission with information about your peer review process – the information you collected at step 1. If you have more than one process, you will repeat this step for each one.
4. Your PRISM peer review submission is checked by the DOAB administrator. Any disputes are referred to the DOAB Scientific Committee. When your submission is accepted, it becomes a PRISM record. If your submission is not approved, the information is deleted.
5. You can now attach your PRISM record to each of your works in DOAB. You may describe more than one peer review process, but you may only attach one process description to each work.
6. Your peer review process information is now available in several ways - see "How can I see PRISM in action?" above.

⁶ <https://www.doabooks.org/en/librarians/metadata-harvesting-and-content-dissemination>

⁷ <https://doabooks.org/en/publishers/documentation>

⁸ <https://www.doabooks.org/en/publishers/join-doab>

7.2. Current documentation for PRISM

This forms part of our DOAB Publishers' guide, available for download⁹. Note: internal links have been removed.

PRISM is a standardised way for academic publishers to display information on DOAB about their peer review processes across their entire catalogue. This guide tells you how to implement PRISM. If you're new to PRISM, start by reading our PRISM overview¹⁰.

Prepare for PRISM

Implementing PRISM is relatively simple – you create a peer review submission (one for each peer review process if you have more than one) in DOAB. Once your submission is checked by a DOAB administrator, it becomes a PRISM record and you can then attach it to relevant works in your collection in DOAB.

Before you start the implementation, it's important to spend time with your colleagues preparing your responses to the peer review questions.

Here are the questions you will need to consider for each peer review process you describe:

1. Title for the peer review process (this will also be the title of your future PRISM record, so give each one a useful name so you can easily tell them apart)
2. Review object: what is being reviewed? Proposal/Full text/Section
3. Anonymity of author(s) and reviewer(s): what is the level of anonymity? Double-anonymised/Single-anonymised/All identities known (Single anonymised review means that the names of the reviewers are hidden from the author; double anonymised review means that both the reviewer and the author are anonymous to each other)
4. Reviewer type: who conducts the review? Internal editor/Editorial board member/External peer reviewer/Crowd or open review
5. Review stage: at what stage is the peer review being conducted? Pre-publication/Post-publication
6. Open review: are the review comments published? Yes/No
7. Publish responsibility: who takes the decision to publish? Publisher/Books or series editor/Scientific or Editorial Board

The OA books landscape is very diverse, with a wide variety of practices across different cultures and disciplines. Therefore, we don't give guidance on best practices in peer

⁹ <https://doabooks.org/en/publishers/documentation>

¹⁰ <https://doabooks.org/en/publishers/prism>

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review, but you can find out more from a general web search, and from these organisations:

- Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE)¹¹
- Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association (OASPA)¹²

Create a peer review record in DOAB

When you log in to DOAB via EGI Check-in, we connect your profile with a named publisher so that you can make edits to that publisher's records. To create new peer review submissions, you therefore need to have permissions for the relevant publisher. This mapping between users, publishers, and peer review submissions is based on the group that each user belongs to. DOAB administrators can't create peer review submissions, as the system wouldn't know to which publisher to connect the submission. However, it is possible for DOAB administrators to log in as another user if necessary.

If you have more than one peer review process, please repeat these steps to create a peer review record for each of your processes.

1. Start from DOAB¹³ and click *Publisher login* at the top right

2. Click *Submissions*

¹¹ <https://publicationethics.org/>

¹² <https://oaspa.org/>

¹³ <https://www.doabooks.org>

MY ACCOUNT

- Logout
- Profile
- Submissions

3. Click *start a new submission*

 [DOAB Home](#) / Submissions

Submissions & Workflow tasks

Submissions

You may [start a new submission](#).

4. Choose the relevant collection: Peer Reviews > Peer Reviews, and click *Next* (the Peer Reviews option will only display for users with the necessary authorisation)

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Item submission

Select a collection

Collection:

Select the collection you wish to submit an item to.

✓ Select a collection...

- Book chapters > Imported or submitted locally
- Books > Imported or submitted locally
- Peer Reviews > Peer Reviews

5. On the **Describe Item** page, respond to each question with the details for your peer review process. It's essential to prepare your answers to these questions with your colleagues before entering your responses. Learn more about preparing for PRISM.
6. Click *Next* to continue (only choose *Save & Exit* if you want to come back to your draft later)
7. On the **Review Submission** page, check the information and make any changes by clicking *Correct one of these*. When everything is correct, click *Complete submission*.
8. Submission complete. Your submission will now go through the review process for this collection. You will receive an e-mail notification as soon as your submission has joined the collection, or if there is a problem with your submission. You may also check on the status of your submission by visiting your submissions page.

Once your peer review record has been checked, you can attach it to a work in your collection by editing its record. You can also add peer review information right at the start when you add a new record.

Attach a peer review record to a work

Once you have at least one peer review record in DOAB, you can attach it to works which have undergone the relevant peer review process.

To attach a peer review record to a work (book or chapter record), follow the steps to edit a record, and use the Peer Review Lookup option.

If you have many titles to update, you may send a .csv file to r.snijder@oapen.org with the relevant information and we will upload it for you - learn more about bulk updates.

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8. Conclusions

We support publishers with documentation (above), a series of webinars for information and discussion. We gather feedback from these and other interactions to gain insights into frequent questions, misunderstandings, or trouble spots, and use these to improve our documentation and communications.

Now that PRISM is in production, activities moving forward will focus on running continual service improvement and dissemination and outreach.